

panicle initiation; P and K were applied basally.

Rice plants were inoculated at panicle initiation to booting stage by placing 21-d-old culture of fungus grown in rice straw between the tillers of each hill at water level.

Fungicides were sprayed 7 d after

inoculation. Disease index (DI) data were recorded at maturity, yield was estimated from a central 2- × 1-m sample of each plot.

Propiconazole and thiophanate methyl + thiram significantly reduced disease severity, with corresponding

increases in yield (see table).

Thiophanate methyl decreased disease incidence with no increase in yield. With thiabendazole, iprodione, thiabendazole + maneb, and edifenphos, yield increased but disease did not decrease significantly. □

Effect of N and K on rice sheath rot (ShR) and crop yield

M. Jayasekhar, Agricultural Research Station, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Paramakudi 623707; and N. N. Prasaid, Faculty of Agriculture, Annamalai University, Tamil Nadu, India

We applied 5 levels of K, 1 level of P, and 2 levels of N in a 15-m² plot for a field trial. Incidence of ShR caused by *Sarocladium oryzae* (Sawada) Gam. was recorded 1 wk before harvest.

Disease incidence (DI) decreased with increased K (see table). Increasing the N level but with no change in P increased DI. □

Rice ShR and yield in Tamil Nadu, India.

Treatment (kg/ha) of			Disease incidence (%)	Decrease (%) over control	Grain yield (kg/plot)
N	P	K			
75	62.5	0	45	–	4.0
75	62.5	50	37	17	4.3
75	62.5	100	26	43	4.6
75	62.5	150	17	62	4.8
75	62.5	200	11	75	5.1
125	62.5	0	50	–	4.4
125	62.5	50	42	16	4.8
125	62.5	100	31	38	4.9
125	62.5	150	21	57	5.4
125	62.5	200	16	68	5.7
LSD (P = 0.01)			3		ns

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Insect management

Using mixtures of buprofezin and cypermethrin or deltamethrin for green leafhopper (GLH) and rice tungro virus (RTV) control

R. F. Macatula, O. Mochida, and J. A. Litsinger, Entomology Department, IRRI

Buprofezin, a slow-acting insectistatic compound, has high activity against *Nephotettix virescens* nymphs and is 50 to 100 times more effective than conventional insecticides. It is slow acting. It does not kill adult insects; only nymphs die during molting to the next instar. Deltamethrin and cypermethrin, which are pyrethroids, have quick knockdown effect on GLH adults.

Table 1. Field evaluation of buprofezin and deltamethrin for GLH control.^a IRRI, 1986.

Insecticide ^b	Rate (g ai/ha)	GLH (no./10 hills) ^c at 1 DAT				Hills (no.) showing RTV symptoms at 65 DT
		1st spraying		2d spraying		
		Adult	Nymph	Adult	Nymph	
Buprofezin 25 WP + deltamethrin 2.5 EC	50 + 6	1.3 ab	0.8 a	1.8 a	39.8 ab	7.5 bc
Buprofezin 25 WP + deltamethrin 2.5 EC	75 + 6	1.3 ab	0.5 a	1.8 a	29.5 ab	6.9 bc
Buprofezin 25 WP + deltamethrin 2.5 EC	6 + 13	1.0 ab	1.0 a	1.8 a	12.0 ab	5.0 bc
Buprofezin 25 WP + deltamethrin 2.5 EC	25 + 13	1.0 ab	0.5 a	0.3 a	15.0 ab	5.4 bc
Buprofezin 25 WP + deltamethrin 2.5 EC	75 + 13	1.0 ab	2.0 a	3.5 ab	8.5 a	5.0 bc
Buprofezin 25 WP	50	2.8 ab	28.8 b	3.3 ab	18.3 ab	10.8 bc
Buprofezin 25 WP	75	3.8 b	24.5 ab	7.0 bc	73.5 bc	13.0 b
Deltamethrin 2.5 EC	13	0.5 a	0.3 a	2.0 a	11.3 ab	6.0 bc
BPMC 50 EC	750	3.0 ab	15.5 ab	4.3 ab	34.8 ab	12.5 b
Untreated		4.0 b	20.0 ab	11.3 c	109.5 c	21.8 a

^a In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^b Insecticides were applied at 20, 35, 50, and 65 DT. Spray volume was 300-500 liters/ha. ^c Av of 4 replications. DAT = days after treatment.

We tested 3 insecticides and their mixtures against GLH populations and RTV infection in 2 separate experiments: buprofezin (6 to 100 g ai/ha) applied alone or in combination with deltamethrin (6 to 13 g ai/ha) or cypermethrin (12.5 to 75 g ai/ha); BPMC was applied at 750 g ai/ha for comparison.

GLH were collected by FARMCOP suction sampler from 10 hills 1 to 2 d after each insecticide application. RTV infection was recorded 65 d after transplanting (DT).

Significantly fewer GLH adults and nymphs were found on plots treated with buprofezin and deltamethrin alone or in combination (Table 1). Even at 50 + 6 g ai/ha, buprofezin- and deltamethrin-treated plots had fewer GLH. BPMC was effective on both GLH adults and nymphs. Buprofezin + deltamethrin at 6 + 13 g ai/ha was as good as higher rates against GLH and RTV.

Buprofezin- and cypermethrin-treated plots had fewer GLH at increasing rates of combination in both EC and WP formulation (Table 2). RTV infection

Table 2. Effect of mixtures of an insectistatic (buprofezin) and a synthetic pyrethroid (cypermethrin) to control GLH and RTV incidence. IRR I, 1986.

Insecticide ^a	Rate (g ai/ha)	GLH (no./10 hills) at 2 DAT ^b				RTV-infected hills (%) at 65 DT
		1st spraying		2d spraying		
		Adult	Nymph	Adult	Nymph	
Buprofezin + cypermethrin 10 + 5 WP	25 + 12.5	2.8 ab	12.8 ab	12.0 b	3.0 a	41 cd
Buprofezin + cypermethrin 10 + 5 WP	50 + 25.0	0.8 ab	6.8 ab	2.8 a	4.5 a	33 abc
Buprofezin + cypermethrin 10 + 5 WP	100 + 50	1.0 ab	5.0 a	1.8 a	2.3 a	24 a
Buprofezin + cypermethrin 10 + 5 WP	25 + 12.5	3.8 b	19.5 b	4.3 ab	1.5 a	38 bcd
Buprofezin + cypermethrin 10 + 5 WP	50 + 25.0	3.0 ab	7.0 ab	2.8 a	2.8 a	32 ab
Buprofezin + cypermethrin 10 + 5 EC	100 + 50.0	1.3 ab	8.3 ab	1.3 a	0.5 a	28 a
Cypermethrin 5 EC	50	0.3 a	5.0 a	1.3 a	4.3 a	27 a
Buprofezin 25 WP	50	4.0 bc	16.0 ab	12.0 b	2.5 a	30 ab
Control		6.8 c	16.0 ab	26.8 c	40.5 b	42 d

^aInsecticides were applied at 10, 30, 50, and 70 DT. Spray volume was 300-500 liters/ha. ^bAv of 4 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. DAT = days after treatment.

was significantly lower on treated plots, except for buprofezin + cypermethrin at 25 + 12.5 g ai/ha in both formulations.

Because typhoons during the reproductive stage caused plants to lodge, yield was not considered. □

Orientation of whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) to scentless rice plants

G. Liu and R. M. Wilkins, Agricultural and Environmental Science Department, University of Newcastle upon Tyne, Newcastle upon Tyne NE1 7RU, UK; and R. C. Saxena, Entomology Department, IRR I

Plant odors act as chemical messengers for insect orientation. Attractants in susceptible rice plants and repellents in resistant plants play an important role in an insect's host selection and establishment. We studied WBPH *Sogatella furcifera* orientation when insects were offered rice plants wrapped in parafilm membrane.

Side tillers of 8-wk-old resistant Rathu Heenati and susceptible TN1 plants in pots were cut off. Half the remaining central tillers were left

Orientation of macropterous *S. furcifera* females to parafilm-wrapped and exposed Rathu Heenati and TN1 rice plants.^a

Treatment	Oriented females ^b (%) at indicated time after release			
	0.5 h	1 h	2 h	4 h
Wrapped TN1	10 a (3)	16 a (8)	15 a (7)	15 a (7)
Exposed TN1	25 b (18)	42 b (45)	57 b (71)	58 b (71)
Exposed Rathu Heenati		43 a (47)	56 a (69)	50 a (59)
Wrapped TN1		21 b (13)	18 b (10)	18 b (10)
Wrapped Rathu Heenati	8a (3)	27 a (21)	32 a (31)	39 a (40)
Wrapped TN1	10 a (4)	26 b (19)	34 a (31)	40 a (41)

^a In a column within a pair, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at P=0.05 (DMRT). ^b Arc sine percentage transformed value. Mean of 5 replications. Figures in parentheses represent actual percentage of females oriented.

exposed and half wrapped with a 5- × 30-cm piece of stretched parafilm (a waterproof, thermoplastic sealing film). Pairs of exposed and wrapped tillers

were inserted into 15- × 30-cm cylindrical mylar cages through small holes in the polystyrene disc that was the common base for the plants. □